

Oral Lichen Planus in a 50-Year-Old Male Patient: A Case Report

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■ Abstract

This paper presents the case of a 50-year-old heavy smoker male with multiple oral white lesions complaining of mild burning sensation in his mouth while consuming acidic foods and liquids. Intraoral examination revealed non-scrapable large white plaque-like lesions with slightly erythematous background on both right and left sides of jugal mucosa, and a white plaque with papillae atrophy at the right lateral border of the tongue. The diagnosis of lichen planus was confirmed through histopathological assessment. Topical corticosteroids were prescribed and symptoms improvement was achieved after two months. Regular annual long-term follow-ups were requested to monitor the disease activity and to exclude any malignant transformation.

Keywords: oral, lichen planus, biopsy, histological examination, topical corticosteroid

Introduction

Oral lichen planus (OLP) is a chronic inflammatory disease that affects the mucous membrane of the oral cavity. It belongs to the mucosal counterpart of cutaneous lichen planus [LP] [1, 2]. The two major clinical forms of OLP are reticular and erosive. Typically, the lesions are multiple, symmetrical, and appear on different sites of the oral cavity [1]. It is more common in the 4th decade of life with slight female predilection [2]. LP of the skin is habitually self-limiting and resolves within 6 months in over 50% of cases and in up to 85% within 18 months. By contrast, nail or scalp LPs as well as OLP are often chronic and may be refractory to treatment [3]. Persistent lesions are considered premalignant. Therefore, patients should be followed up regularly for both, adjustment of treatment, and screening for the development of malignancies [3]. In this report, we present the case of a 50-year-old male diagnosed with OLP.

Case presentation

A 50-year-old male was referred by his dentist to our specialized oral medicine clinic for evaluation of multiple oral white lesions. Mild burning sensation while having acidic foods and liquids was his chief complaint. Medical history was unremarkable, and physical examination revealed no extra-oral abnormal findings. He was a heavy smoker (30 cigarettes per day) for more than 20 years. On clinical examination, the patient presented non-scrapable large white plaque-like lesions with slightly erythematous background on both right and left sides of jugal mucosa. Additionally, at the right lateral border of the tongue, a white plaque with papillae atrophy was noticed (Figures 1 and 2).

Based on the clinical presentation and the accompanying symptoms a provisional diagnosis of OLP was given. The lesions were biopsied under local anesthesia, fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin, and sent for histological examination. The histopathology report disclosed a thickened stratified epithelium, with irregular acanthosis and hyperparakeratosis

Figure 1. Intraoral photographs showing the bilateral (A: left; B: right) jugal white lesions.

Figure 2. Intraoral photograph showing the white lesion with papillae atrophy at the right lateral border of the tongue

and formation of parakeratosis foci. Rich band-like inflammatory infiltrate consisting of mononuclear cells was identified in the lamina propria, just below the epithelium with perturbation of the basement membrane integrity. This histological aspect was consistent with OLP.

The diagnosis of OLP was confirmed and since the case presented mild symptoms, topical use of corticosteroids (twice daily for 2 months) was prescribed and symptoms improvement was achieved. Regular annual long-term follow-ups were requested to monitor the disease activity and to exclude any malignant transformation.

Discussion

Lichen planus is a chronic mucocutaneous inflammatory lesion which may affect the skin, the nails, the scalp, the lips, and other mucosal surfaces including the oral mucosa, the esophagus, the pharynx, and the genital mucosa (the glans penis, the vulvar and vaginal mucosa, the labia majora, and the labia minora) [3]. OLP is relatively frequent in adult patients. Its etiology remains unknown, but stress, drugs, dental fillings, genetic factors, immunity, and hyper-sensitivity reactions can be contributing factors to its pathogenesis [1]. Many studies have supposed that OLP is a T cell-mediated autoimmune condition, in which cytotoxic CD8+ T-cells that release different cytokines like TNF α and interleukin-12 (IL-12) may

cause the perturbation of the lining epithelial basement membrane integrity [4]. Drugs such as antimalarials, ACEIs, thiazide diuretics, NSAIDs, quinidine, beta-blockers, tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF α) inhibitors [5], as well as contact allergens, and viruses, especially the hepatitis C virus (HCV), have all been reported to be possibly associated with development of LP [6, 7]. Additionally, OLP has been linked to a variety of metals found in dental restorations including mercury, copper, and gold [8].

Clinically, LP appears as pruritic, violaceous papules and plaques most frequently found on the wrists, lower back, and ankles [6]. A specific lattice-like network of white lines called Wickham striae could be observed overlying the lesions [3]. On the other hand, six types of OLP, namely reticular, papular, plaque-like, atrophic/erosive, ulcerative, and bullous can be identified [9]. The jugal mucosa, the tongue and the gingiva are frequently involved although other sites may be rarely affected [10]. OLP may present alone or associated with skin lesions. It is often asymptomatic. However, it may be complicated by painful erosions; burning sensation may also occur. Microscopically, it is characterized by lymphocytic infiltrate and vacuolar degeneration of the epithelial basal layer [3].

The prevalence of cutaneous LP is around 0.2% to 1% of adults globally [11]. OLP is more frequent and reported in 1% to 4% of the population, with female to male ratio of 1.5:1. Most of LP cases develop between the ages of 30 and 60 [12]. While LP is not usually considered to have a racial predilection, some studies have suggested a higher incidence of the disease in African-Americans, Indian and Arabian descents [13, 14]. Additionally, a familial component of up to 10% of first-degree relatives has been proposed [15].

The differential diagnosis includes lichenoid lesions (drug related or caused by the contact with restorative dental materials), leukoplakia, lupus erythematosus, pemphigus vulgaris, mucous membrane pemphigoid, secondary syphilis, traumatic patches, and candidiasis [3].

OLP is habitually difficult to treat, especially when wide erosions are present. Topical corticosteroids are the treatment of choice. They can be applied twice daily for 1 to 2 months, and then administered as required. Intralesional steroid injections are considered when

lesions are particularly painful and fail to respond to topical therapy [3, 16]. Systemic corticosteroids are reserved for patients with severe erosive OLP [16]. Other systemic treatments are retinoids, cyclosporine, azathioprine, hydroxychloroquine, methotrexate, thalidomide, and/or use of topical calcineurin inhibitors [3, 16]. To reduce pain, mouthwash based on a lidocaine solution may be helpful. Recently, low level laser was used to decrease erosive OLP symptoms. Amphotericin B can be used several times daily (after food consumption) to prevent secondary candida infection. OLP may clear spontaneously within years, but usually it presents a remitting and relapsing course [3]. Long-term follow-up is indispensable to

observe disease activity and to rule out any potential malignant transformation [3, 16].

Conclusion

OLP is an immune disease with unknown etiology. In order to improve its management, an early accurate diagnosis through histological examination is needed. In our case, the clinical evolution was favorable after the administration of topical corticosteroids. Regular postoperative follow-ups are mandatory for optimum treatment outcome and recurrence/malignant transformation prevention.

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